

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on Suitability maps for grapevines and supplementary crops for actual and future climatic conditions at pilot sites

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

DELIVERABLE D1.3 - DELIVERABLE D1.4

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Contents

GLOSSARY.....	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
INTRODUCTION.....	5
OLTREPÒ PAVESE PILOT SITES: SELECTION OF INDICATORS.....	6
SOIL SURVEY CARRIED OUT BY ERSAF	7
ASSESSMENT OF RELATIVE WEIGHT FOR THE SELECTED INDICATORS	8
RESULTS FOR THE OLTREPÒ PAVESE PILOT SITES.....	10
SOIL SUITABILITY AT PILOT SITES	12
TOPOGRAPHIC SUITABILITY AT PILOT SITES	16
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY AT PILOT SITES	20
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULTS FOR PILOT SITES ACTUAL SCENARIO (BASELINE [1991–2020]).....	23
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULTS FOR PILOT SITES FUTURE SCENARIOS.....	27
TOTAL SUITABILITY METHODOLOGY FOR PILOT SITES.....	37
TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS FOR PILOT SITES (ACTUAL SCENARIO)	38
TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS OF PILOT SITES (FUTURE SCENARIOS).....	41
REFERENCES.....	52

Glossary

Definition	
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D1.2) presents the integrated analysis of bioclimatic, soil and topographic indicators developed at microscale in 4 pilot sites of Oltrepò Pavese, in Lombardy, with the objective of producing synthetic suitability maps for vineyards under current and future climatic conditions, drawn up with specific soil and topographic data, collected at the individual pilot sites. The work at the pilot site level also has the aim of validating the suitability obtained at the macroscale and reported in D1.1.

The activity was carried out adopting the same methodology proposed by CMCC and UNISS for the study of viticultural suitability in Sardinia (described in D1.1), appropriately adapted to the local characteristics of the investigated territory, as detailed in the following chapters.

The bioclimatic indicators provided by CMCC were acquired and processed at very high spatial resolution (2.2 km), based on the analyses developed within RM8 and described in deliverable D8.3. Using these data provided for the Oltrepò Pavese area, the University of Pavia elaborated the climatic suitability maps under current and future conditions. ERSAF produced the soil and topographic suitability maps, which were shared with the University of Pavia for integration with the climatic framework and for generating the final suitability map for each pilot site. The integrated maps — climatic, soil and topographic — are included in the activities planned within the Flagship Project VINO part of NODES Spoke 6 RM1 – Title: Maps of suitability for the grapevine cultivation and for cultivations alternative/supplementary to grapevine.

Introduction

Detailed information on the methodology shared by CMCC and UNISS is provided in [DELIVERABLE_D1.1_Suitability current_and future conditions_at Macro-scale](#), where the various steps leading to the suitability analysis are explained in detail.

In particular they are described there the selection of indicators and the assessment of the relative weights

As described by CMCC in Deliverable 1.1, bioclimatic information is provided for climate change impact analyses on vineyards or other cultivations characterized by high spatial and temporal resolution. Bioclimatic indicators are derived using atmospheric variables from climate projections, based on dynamic downscaling of regional climate models produced by CMCC.

Agricultural land suitability is determined by combining crop requirements and soil and other environmental attributes. Assessing how well the properties of a land unit align with the demands of a specific land use by farming activities results in its suitability. Thus, 'suitability'

quantifies the degree to which the characteristics of a parcel of land align with the requisites of a particular crop (FAO, 1976).

The objective of the work is to integrate bioclimatic indices with soil and topography parameters to develop a GIS-based vineyard suitability analysis referring to a specific production target. To our knowledge, few studies have been realized until now combining different bioclimatic indices, soil and topographical qualifiers, and land use information to assess land vineyard suitability.

The method is based on a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM), and is consistent with the FAO land suitability evaluation; for this reason the study area has been classified into five classes based on its suitability: S1 – “Highly Suitable”, S2 – “Moderately Suitable”, S3 – “Marginally Suitable”, N1 – “Currently Not Suitable” and N2 – “Permanently Not Suitable”.

Oltrepò Pavese Pilot sites: selection of indicators

To establish a standardized methodological framework for Oltrepò Pavese area, ERSAF adopted the same approach previously described at the Macro-scale.

The bioclimatic indicators for current and future climate conditions calculated separately by CMCC for the Oltrepò study area, were then represented in a single climate suitability map by UNIPV, adopting the established weights, to assess the current suitability of the pilot sites for viticulture and to predict their potential for cultivation over time. Climatic maps are essential for assessing land suitability for viticulture, as they provide a precise and contextualized representation of the climatic variables influencing vine growth. The methodology allowed the generation of an updated depiction of current climate conditions and their implications for viticulture in the region, to be integrated with the soil and topographical suitability assessments carried out by ERSAF. A detailed description of the maps is provided in a dedicated chapter.

The weight of the first level analysis, "macro-factors," was modified in consideration of the specific characteristics of the study area. Among the macro-factors considered, topography has the greatest impact, together with climate, due to the morphological features of the territory that directly influence viticultural suitability. The soil macro-factor, while playing an important role in determining vine adaptability, was considered to have a lower impact compared to the other macro-factors, as *Vitis vinifera* exhibits a considerable capacity to adapt to a wide range of soil conditions. Furthermore, since the assessment is not specific to a particular cultivar or oenological production, it allows for broad flexibility across diverse pedoclimatic conditions.

In the overall Suitability assessment, ERSAF addressed specifically the soil and topographic components; within the soil macro-factor ERSAF modified specific pedological parameters and adjusted the class thresholds to better reflect the distinct environmental characteristics of the Oltrepò Pavese region. The pedological parameters considered most relevant for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese region are:

- soil depth,
- pH,
- soil texture,
- Total CaCO₃,
- soil organic carbon.

The same approach was applied to the topography macro-factor. ERSAF considered the same indicators previously selected, reclassified according to the specific territorial characteristics of the Oltrepò Pavese area:

- elevation,
- slope
- exposure (orientation)

Soil survey carried out by ERSAF

The soil survey carried out by ERSAF, as part of RM1-Task1.3, have significantly enhanced the current understanding of the main pedological parameters of the Oltrepò Pavese region. The aim was to assess the suitability of vineyards at a scale corresponding to the pilot sites. Four experimental sites were selected in collaboration with Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of the University of Pavia, where field investigations were conducted using a manual auger.

This investigation involved the execution of 31 sampling points, distributed across four sites located in the Oltrepò Pavese area, specifically in the municipalities of Montù Beccaria, Costa Cavalieri, Canevino, and Santa Maria della Versa.

The sampling phase included the drilling of boreholes using a manual auger, which allowed the examination of some soil characteristics at varying depths, typically ranging from 100 to 120 cm, depending on the soil depth. This method enabled the observation of key features such as color, potential pigmentation variations caused by rubefaction, brunification or redox processes, secondary concentrations (carbonates, ferromanganese, etc.), a preliminary estimate of granulometry, and the presence and size of roots and pores. Collectively, these observations facilitate the preliminary identification of stratifications resulting from various pedogenic processes, providing advice on the appropriate depth to explore root systems and identify potential limitations (e.g., shallow water table, drainage problems, massive and compact horizons, etc.).

Each borehole was georeferenced and assigned a unique identification code. For each soil horizon identified and described in the borehole, soil samples were collected for subsequent chemical and physical laboratory analysis. The data obtained from these analyses, associated with

the georeferenced boreholes sampled in each pilot site, were then compiled into a database. The database consists of the values of each parameter considered as weighted averages over the 0–100 cm soil thickness or over the useful soil depth if this is shallower (one parameter value for each borehole point), which serves as a foundation for defining the soil characteristics of each investigated site. These data are essential for assessing the soil suitability in the pilot sites, utilizing the Geographic Information System (GIS) for cartographic data processing.

Assessment of relative weight for the selected indicators

To assess the suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese ERSAF applied the Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) approach, described in a former paragraph, proposed by the CMCC to assess the suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese.

However, considering the specific characteristics of the investigated area, ERSAF developed its own weighting table, incorporating the different classes and the pedological and topographic parameters relevant to the study area. This adaptation ensures that the analysis accurately reflects the distinct environmental features of the Oltrepò Pavese viticulture region while maintaining methodological consistency with the CMCC approach.

As previously highlighted, the weight assigned to the first level of analysis, relating to the integration of macro-factors, has been modified based on the specific characteristics of the study area. Specifically, the weight of the topography has been increased and that of the soil has been reduced, while the weight previously assigned to climate has been only minimally reduced, remaining the predominant, as shown in the table below.

1° LEVEL	CATEGORY	WEIGHT (%)	WEIGHT
Macro-factors	Climate	50	0.5
	Soil	15	0.15
	Topography	35	0.35

At the second level, the bioclimatic indices remained the same as those used by the CMCC, although the weight of each parameter was modified by UNIPV, with all indices assigned the same weight.

Regarding the soil, the weights of each pedological parameter were adjusted by ERSAF based on their relevance to the study area, and the classification thresholds were updated to more accurately determine land suitability.

Regarding topography, the parameters and their weights were kept unchanged; however, they were reclassified to better align with the specific characteristics of the Oltrepò Pavese region.

2° LEVEL	CATEGORY	VALUE	POINTS	SUITABILITY CLASS	WEIGHT (%)	OVERALL WEIGHT
Climate	Cool night Index	12–14	1	S1	20	0.10%
		14–18	2	S2		
		6–12 / 18–25	3	S3		
		<6; >25	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Huglin	2100–2400	1	S1	20	0.10%
		1800–2100; 2400–2700	2	S2		
		1500–1800; 2700–3000	3	S3		
		1200–1500	4	N1		
		<1200; >3000	5	N2		
	Frost Free Days	>200	1	S1	20	0.10%
		180–200	2	S2		
		160–180	3	S3		
		140–160	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Dryness Index	50–(-100)	1	S1	20	0.10%
		(-100)–(-200)	2	S2		
		<-200; 50–150	3	S3		
		>150	4	N1		
			5	N2		
BEDD	1600–1800	1	S1	20	0.10%	
	1400–1600; 1800–2000	2	S2			
	1200–1400; 2000–2200	3	S3			
	1000–1200	4	N1			
	<1000; >2200	5	N2			

2° LEVEL	CATEGORY	VALUE	POINTS	SUITABILITY CLASS	WEIGHT (%)	OVERALL WEIGHT
Soil	Depth cm	> 80	1	S1	29	4.35%
		60–80	2	S2		
		30–60	3	S3		
		≤30	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	pH ph unit	5.3 -8.0	1	S1	14	2.1%
		5.0-5.2; 8.1-8.3	2	S2		

		4.4-4.9; 8.4-8.5	3	S3	29	4.35%	
		<4.4; ≥8.5	4	N1			
			5	N2			
		FA - FSA - F	1	S1			
		FLA - FS - AS	2	S2			
	Texture USDA class	SF - AL - FL - A	3	S3			
		S - L	4	N1			
			5	N2			
		Total CaCO ₃ %	≤ 20	1	S1	15	2.25%
			20 - 35	2	S2		
	35 - 40		3	S3			
	>40		4	N1			
			5	N2			
	OM %	≥ 2	1	S1	13	1.95%	
		1 - 2	2	S2			
0,6 - 1		3	S3				
0,4 - 0,6		4	N1				
<0,4		5	N2				
Topography	Elevation m a.s.l.	120-400	1	S1	33.33	11.7%	
		400-600	2	S2			
		600-900	3	S3			
		≤120; >900	4	N1			
			5	N2			
	Aspect °N	S-SE (112,5-202,5)	1	S1	33.33	11.7%	
		SW-E (202,5-247,5; 67,5-112,5)	2	S2			
		W-NE (247,5-292,5; 22,5-67,5)	3	S3			
		NW-N (292,5-22,5)	4	N1			
			5	N2			
	Slope %	2-20	1	S1	33.33	11.7%	
		20-35	2	S2			
		35-45	3	S3			
		≤2; >45	4	N1			
			5	N2			

Results for the Oltrepò Pavese Pilot sites

This section presents the of soil and topographic suitability maps results for the four pilot sites identified.

The soil and topography parameters used for the suitability, are shown in the previous chapter. The overall viticulture suitability assessment will be obtained by integrating all macro-factors suitability maps: **soil** and **topography**, calculated by ERSAF, with the **climate** suitability maps,

elaborated by the Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of the University of Pavia, using the same bioclimatic indices and classes previously adopted by the CMCC for the climatic assessment of the Sardinian territory.

Below are presented the maps resulting from the analysis of pedological and topographic suitability. The rasters of the pedological suitability maps have a cell size of 3x3 m.

The rasters of the topographic suitability maps have a cell size of 20x20 m, derived from the Digital Terrain Model (DTM), which was used as the primary data source for cartographic processing.

Within the NODES–RM1 project, viticultural suitability was assessed at two complementary levels: the Macroscale and the Pilot Site scale. The Macroscale analysis the assessment of a large territory examined at a provincial scale with a semi-detailed representation at a scale of 1:50,000. This information density provides overall information on the investigated territory but does not adequately represent local soil and topographic variability. In the case of soil suitability, it allows for the identification of significant territorial patterns and differences, while offering mainly general indications due to the relatively low density of available soil data.

The Pilot Site assessment, by contrast, benefits from more detailed information derived from site-specific data collected by ERSAF during the 2024 monitoring campaign described in the previous chapters, allowing for a more precise characterization of local pedological soil features. However, regardless of the scale considered, the suitability assessment should be interpreted as an orientative tool, supporting the identification of favourable or potentially limiting conditions for grapevine cultivation. For instance, a “moderately suitable” class indicates territorial contexts that do not preclude the achievement of high-quality production and agronomic performance. The purpose of the resulting maps is therefore not to definitively exclude areas classified as S2, S3 or even N1 — which reflect more pronounced limitations — but rather to report these limitations, providing useful information for planning and the opportunity or need for potential mitigation measures, which must in any case be evaluated in relation to oenological objectives and grape variety choices.

The Pilot Site assessment allows the territorial characterization to be further refined, providing a higher level of detail, confirming the limitations identified at the Macroscale or, alternatively, detecting favourable soil or topographic features that cannot emerge at a provincial scale. Finally, it is important to underline that the interpretation of the results presented in the following chapters does not provide a definitive assessment of the suitability of an area; instead, it provides a preliminary territorial evaluation that should be complemented with field-scale investigations to confirm local conditions and deepen the understanding of the viticultural potential.

Soil suitability at Pilot sites

As shown in the summary table and the corresponding maps, the four pilot sites fall into the suitability classes S1 and S2, corresponding to the "Highly Suitable" and "Moderately suitable" categories, respectively. The parameters were evaluated individually, reclassified based on the threshold values for each class as indicated in the table, and subsequently summarized by applying the weights reported in the table of the previous chapter, thus determining the final assessment of pedological suitability.

The **Canevino pilot site** has 100% of its total surface area classified as S2 – Moderately Suitable. This homogeneous classification is mainly driven by the "Effective Soil Depth" parameter, where the S1 (>80 cm) and S2 (60–80 cm) classes have comparable extents. Furthermore, the "Total CaCO₃" content across the site remains predominantly within the S1 – "Highly suitable" threshold (≤20%), reinforcing the overall suitability.

A similar trend is observed for the other pedological parameters: the site is entirely classified as S2 in terms of soil texture; organic matter falls mostly within the S2 class, with a limited presence of S1; and pH also shows a predominance of S2 values.

The absence of Highly Suitable (S1) areas in the soil suitability map is due to the requirement that all five pedological parameters must simultaneously fall within the S1 class for a pixel to be considered "Highly Suitable". Nevertheless, the site maintains a consistently favourable pedological profile for viticulture.

At the **Costa Cavalieri pilot site**, 93.0% of the total surface area is classified as S2 – "Moderately Suitable", while a small portion (7%) falls within the S1 – "Highly Suitable" class. This distribution reflects generally favourable pedological conditions for viticulture, with only minor limitations.

The predominance of S2 is primarily associated with the Organic Matter parameter, which largely falls within the 1–2% range (S2), as well as the pH values (5.0–5.2 / 8.1–8.3) and Texture classes (FLA – FS – AS), all of which contribute to the S2 classification.

The presence of a small S1 portion "Highly Suitable", confirm the overall pedological profile suitable for viticultural.

At the **Santa Maria della Versa pilot site**, 100% of the total area is classified as S2 – "Moderately Suitable". Despite the absence of areas in the Very Suitable (S1) category, the site still presents a generally favourable pedological profile for viticulture, with no significant limiting factors.

The predominance of the S2 class is mainly driven by the following parameters:

Texture: mostly classified as S2 (Clay Loam, Sandy Loam, Sandy Clay Loam).

Organic matter predominantly falls within the S2 class (1.0–2.0%), with a small portion of the area classified as S1 (≥2.0%). The pH values obtained from soil analyses indicate a classification mainly within the S2 range (5.0–5.2 / 8.1–8.3), with limited occurrences of S1 (5.3–8). Total CaCO₃ content is largely within the S2 suitability class (20–35%), although a smaller share of the area falls into the S3 category, with values ranging between 35% - 40%. Although the parameter "Effective Soil Depth" is classified as S1 across most of the site—an important factor due to its 29% weight in the

overall suitability index—this alone is not sufficient to elevate the final classification to Highly Suitable. This is because a pixel must fall within the S1 class for all five pedological parameters simultaneously to be categorized as S1. Therefore, the integrated evaluation results in a dominant S2 classification.

The **Montù Beccaria pilot site** exhibits overall favourable pedological conditions for viticulture, with 100% of the total surface area classified as S2 – “Moderately Suitable”. This distribution is mainly influenced by the Effective Soil Depth parameter, with most of the area falling into the S1 class (>80 cm), a significant portion into S2 (60–80 cm). Total CaCO₃ values are predominantly within the S2 class (20–35%), although the S1 class (≤20%) is also represented. Organic Matter is largely classified as S2 (1.0–2.0%), and the pH parameter shows a distribution mostly within the S2 class, with partial presence in S1 – Very Suitable. As previously described, the absence of areas classified as S1 – Very Suitable is because no pixel simultaneously meets the suitability thresholds for all five pedological parameters considered.

The predominance of "Moderately Suitable" class observed in all four investigated pilot sites was an expected result, given that the pilot sites are in an area historically known for its strong viticultural vocation. However, for a comprehensive assessment of viticultural suitability, it is essential to integrate **topographic and climatic components**, as these can significantly influence the overall suitability of the pilot sites.

Pilot Site	S1 (ha)	S2 – (ha)	% S1	% S2	Sup. Tot. (ha)
	Highly suitable	Moderately Suitable			
Canevino	/	2,7	/	100	2,7
Costa Cavalieri	0,23	3,14	7,0	93,0	3,4
Santa Maria della Versa	/	2,40	/	100	2,4
Montù Beccaria	/	15,5	/	100	15,5

Canevino

Costa Cavalieri

Santa Maria della Versa

Montù Beccaria

Topographic suitability at Pilot sites

The topographic suitability assessment was conducted by considering three key parameters: slope, exposure, and altitude. These parameters were derived from the Digital Terrain Model (DTM), which was used as the primary data source for cartographic processing. Consequently, the raster of the topographic suitability maps has a 20x20 meter resolution.

The entire surface of the **Canevino pilot site**, covering 2.7 hectares, is classified as S2 – “Moderately Suitable” in terms of topographic suitability. This classification results from the combined assessment of the three topographic parameters considered: slope, altitude, and aspect. Specifically, slope values across the site fall within the S2 class (20–35%), indicating slopes that are favourable for viticulture. With respect to altitude, the entire site falls within the 120–400 m a.s.l. range, corresponding to the S1 – “Highly Suitable” class, which represents optimal elevation conditions for high-quality hillside viticulture. The “aspect” parameter, on the other hand, predominantly falls within the S3 – Moderately Suitable class, suggesting a sub-optimal orientation that, while not ideal, remains compatible with viticultural requirements. The integration of these three factors results in an overall S2 topographic suitability classification, indicating conditions that are generally well-suited for quality wine production.

The entire surface of the **Costa Cavalieri pilot site**, covering 3.4 hectares, is classified within the S2 – “Moderately Suitable” topographic suitability class. This classification reflects the evaluation based on the three topographic parameters considered: altitude, slope, and aspect. The site is entirely located within the 400–600 m a.s.l. elevation range, corresponding to the S2 class for altitude. The aspect parameter contributes positively to the overall assessment, with a large portion of the area showing south to southeast orientations, which fall within the S1 – “Highly Suitable” and S2 – “Moderately Suitable” classes. Slope analysis indicates that a large portion of the area falls within the range of gradients (20–35%), corresponding to the S2 – “Moderately Suitable” class, although some smaller areas exhibit gentler slope that fall into the S1 – “Highly Suitable” class. The combination of these parameters places the entire site within the S2 class, indicating generally favourable topographic conditions for viticulture. It is also worth noting that Costa Cavalieri is currently the only pilot site not planted with vineyards, as it is maintained as permanent grassland.

In the **Santa Maria della Versa pilot site**, covering 2.4 hectares, 85.5% of the total surface is classified as S3 – “Marginally Suitable”, 10% as S2 – “Moderately Suitable”, and only 2.9% as S1 – “Highly” Suitable. This distribution results from the combined influence of slope, altitude, and aspect. Although the site lies entirely within the 120–400 m a.s.l. range, corresponding to the S1 class for the altitude parameter, the overall suitability is significantly reduced by the site's aspect, predominantly oriented towards north/northwest, which falls into the N1 – Temporarily Not Suitable class. As for slope, most of the surface presents moderate gradients (20–35%), aligning with the S2 – “Moderately Suitable” class. The interaction of these parameters results in a dominant S3 classification, with a limited area classified as Suitable (S2) and Very Suitable (S1).

In the **Montù Beccaria pilot site**, which covers a total area of 15.5 hectares, 93.5% of the surface is classified as S2 – “Moderately Suitable”, 6.5% as S2 – “Marginally Suitable” and 0.2% as N1 – “Currently Not Suitable” in terms of topographic suitability. This distribution indicates overall favourable conditions for viticulture, largely driven by the site’s classification as “Highly Suitable” (S1) for altitude, as it falls predominantly within the 120–400 m a.s.l. range. However, it should be noted that the areas classified as N1 correspond to zones located below 120 m a.s.l., which fall into the “Currently Not Suitable” altitude class and therefore account for the 0.2% of surface area attributed to this category in the resulting map. Regarding the aspect parameter, the slope is predominantly oriented towards south and southeast, which are considered optimal for grapevine cultivation. The slope parameter shows a balanced distribution between S1 (2–20%) and S2 (20–25%) classes, with only a marginal portion falling into S3 (35–45%). The combination of these factors results in a site that is predominantly suitable for quality viticulture, with a substantial portion falling within the most favourable suitability classes.

Pilot Site	S1 (ha)	S2 – (ha)	S3 (ha)	N1 (ha)	% S1	% S2	% S3	% N1	Sup. Tot. (ha)
	Highly suitable	Moderately Suitable	Marginally Suitable	Currently Not Suitable					
Canevino	-	2,7	-	-	-	100	-	-	2,7
Costa Cavalieri	-	3,4	-	-	-	100	-	-	3,4
Santa Maria della Versa	0,07	0,24	2,1	-	2,9	10	85,5	-	2,4
Montù Beccaria	-	14,49	1,01	0,03		93,5	6,5	0,2	15,5

Canevino

Costa Cavalieri

Santa Maria della Versa

Montù Beccaria

Climatic suitability at Pilot sites

The assessment of climatic suitability at the pilot sites was conducted using the same GIS-based Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) methodology as applied at the macro-scale level. This approach, applied in collaboration with CMCC, is based on the integration of five bioclimatic indicators selected for their relevance to viticultural performance.

The evaluation was carried out for four pilot sites located in the Oltrepò Pavese region, specifically in the municipalities of:

- 1- Canevino
- 2-Costa Cavalieri
- 3-Montù Beccaria
- 4-Santa Maria della Versa

Each site was analyzed under current (baseline) climatic conditions.

The climatic suitability assessment was based on five bioclimatic indicators selected for their relevance to grapevine development: Cool Night Index (CNI), Huglin Index (HI), Frost Free Days (FFD), Dryness Index (DI), and Biologically Effective Degree Days (BEDD). Each indicator was reclassified into suitability classes (S1-N2) according to threshold values derived from viticultural literature and adapted to the Oltrepò Pavese case study.

Indicator weighting followed a GIS-based MCE in which ERSAF adjusted the pedological parameters based on its expertise and expert guidance, while the climatic weights were suggested by CMCC during the last meeting; the table below presents the value ranges, thresholds, suitability classes, and weights for each indicator.

2° LEVEL	CATEGORY	VALUE	POINTS	SUITABILITY CLASS	WEIGHT (%)	OVERALL WEIGHT
Clima	Cool night Index	12-14	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		14-18	2	S2		
		6-12/18-25	3	S3		
		<6; >25	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Huglin	2100–2400	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		1800–2100; 2400–2700	2	S2		
		1500–1800; 2700–3000	3	S3		
		1200–1500	4	N1		
		<1200; ≥ 3000	5	N2		
	Frost Free Days	>200	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		180–200	2	S2		
		160–180	3	S3		
		140–160	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Dryness Index	50-(-100)	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		(-100)-(-200)	2	S2		
		<-200;50-150	3	S3		
		>150	4	N1		
			5	N2		
BEDD	1600–1800	1	S1	20 %	10.4%	
	1400–1600; 1800–2000	2	S2			
	1200–1400; 2000–2200	3	S3			
	1000–1200	4	N1			
	<1000; >2200	5	N2			

The five bioclimatic indicators used were:

1-Cool Night Index (CNI)

2-Huglin Index (HI)

3-Frost Free Days (FFD)

4-Dryness Index (DI)

5-Biologically Effective Degree Days (BEDD)

These indicators were derived from high resolution (3 km) downscaled climate data provided by references. Each raster was reclassified into five suitability classes (S1 to N2), based on thresholds defined through viticultural literature and expert knowledge.

The indicators were then weighted according to their relative importance in determining viticultural suitability:

Dryness Index (DI)	20 %
Huglin Index (HI)	20 %
BEDD	20 %
FFD	20 %
CNI	20 %

Weighted rasters were combined using raster algebra in QGIS to generate a synthetic climatic suitability map for each pilot site. The continuous output raster was reclassified into five discrete classes using fixed thresholds:

S1 (Highly Suitable)	0.00 – 1.00
S2 (Suitable)	1.01 – 2.00
S3 (Moderately Suitable)	2.01 – 3.00
N1 (Currently Not Suitable)	3.01 – 4.00
N2 (Permanently Not Suitable)	>4.00

This process enabled a spatially explicit assessment of climate-based viticultural suitability under current conditions at the individual site level, which will later be integrated with pedological and topographical suitability evaluations.

Climatic Suitability for pilot sites – Future Scenarios

This section evaluates the climatic suitability of the Oltrepò Pavese region for viticulture under projected future climate conditions, furnished by CMCC in Deliverable D8.3. The analysis was performed at the macro scale using four climate scenarios:

- 1-RCP 45 (2021–2050)
- 2-RCP 45 (2036–2065)
- 3-RCP 85 (2021–2050)
- 4-RCP 85 (2036–2065)

The methodological framework was identical to that used for the baseline assessment, ensuring full comparability between present and future conditions.

Climatic Suitability Results for Pilot Sites Actual Scenario (Baseline [1991–2020])

The results demonstrate a differentiated outcome across the pilot sites, reflecting varying levels of suitability under current conditions. While none of the sites exhibit severe or permanent constraints (N1 or N2), they also lack areas of optimal conditions (S1). Instead, the distribution is split between S2 (Moderately Suitable) and S3 (Marginally Suitable).

Site-by-site summary:

Canevino: The entirety of the site (100%) is classified as S2 (Moderately Suitable).

Costa Cavalieri: Similarly, 100% of the site falls within S2 (Moderately Suitable).

Montù Beccaria: The site shows a mixed distribution, with 51.39% of the area in S2 (Moderately Suitable) and 48.61% in S3 (Marginally Suitable).

Santa Maria della Versa: The full extent of the site (100%) is classified as S3 (Marginally Suitable).

Overall, this updated classification illustrates the variability of viticultural potential across the pilot sites. While Canevino and Costa Cavalieri present the most favorable outcomes (fully in S2), Montù Beccaria demonstrates a balanced mix of moderately and marginally suitable conditions, and Santa Maria della Versa remains constrained within S3

Pilot Site	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Montù Beccaria	0.00	51.39%	48.61%	0.00	0.00
Costa Cavalieri	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Canevino	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Santa Maria della Versa	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

The bar chart shows a differentiated pattern across the four pilot sites under current climatic conditions. Canevino and Costa Cavalieri are entirely classified within S2 – Moderately Suitable (100% each). Montù Beccaria displays a split distribution, with 51.39% in S2 – Moderately Suitable and 48.61% in S3 – Marginally Suitable. Santa Maria della Versa remains uniformly in S3 – Marginally Suitable (100%). No areas fall into S1 – Highly Suitable, N1 – Currently Not Suitable, or N2 – Permanently Not Suitable, indicating that while optimal zones are absent, prohibitive climatic constraints are also not present. This differentiated classification underscores the value of integrating other macro-factors, particularly soil and topography, previously shown to be favorable, to fully characterize the viticultural potential of each site.

Actual Climatic Suitability Pilot Sites MAPS

Canevino:

Costa Cavalieri:

Montù Beccaria:

Santa Maria della Versa:

Climatic Suitability Results for Pilot Sites Future Scenarios

The climatic suitability outputs for the four pilot sites under the four future climate Scenarios: RCP 45 (2021–2050), RCP 45 (2036–2065), RCP 85 (2021–2050), and RCP 85 (2036–2065), indicate a strong dominance of class 3 (S3 – marginally suitable) across all sites and scenarios.

Site: Costa Cavalieri (CCV)

In all four scenarios, 100% of the site area is classified as S3 (marginally suitable), with no pixels in higher suitability classes (S1–S2) or in the lower classes, N1 (class 4, currently not suitable) and N2 (permanently not suitable). This suggests that, under both moderate (RCP 45) and high (RCP 85) emission trajectories, the projected changes in the considered climatic indices consistently support a marginal suitability status across the entire site.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Costa Cavalieri Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2021–2050):

Costa Cavalieri Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2036–2065):

Costa Cavalieri Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2021–2050):

Costa Cavalieri Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2036–2065):

Site: Canevino (CNV)

The suitability classification for the entire Canevino (CNV) site varies depending on the emission trajectory. Under the moderate emission trajectory (RCP 45), 100% of the site area is consistently classified as S2 (Moderately Suitable) across both time horizons (2021–2050 and 2036–2065). However, under the high emission trajectory (RCP 85), 100% of the site area shifts to S3 (Marginally Suitable) for the same periods. This indicates that while the site maintains a suitable status in all future scenarios, the increase in emissions leads to a reduction in the degree of suitability, suggesting that the projected climatic conditions intensify the identified limiting factors under the higher RCP 85 scenario.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Canevino	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	100	0	0	0
Canevino	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	100	0	0	0
Canevino	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Canevino	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Canevino Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2021–2050):

Canevino Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2036–2065):

Canevino Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2021–2050):

Canevino Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2036–2065):

Site: Montù Beccaria (POR)

The Montù Beccaria (POR) site area is consistently classified entirely within S3 (marginally suitable) for all four future scenarios, showing no shift towards either higher suitability classes (S1–S2) or lower classes (N1–N2).

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Montù Beccaria	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Montù Beccaria Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2021–2050)

Montù Beccaria Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2036–2065)

Montù Beccaria Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2021–2050)

Montù Beccaria Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2036–2065)

Site: Santa Maria della Versa (SMV)

This area is consistently classified entirely within S3 (marginally suitable) under all four future scenarios. The absence of any class variation between scenarios suggests that the site will get a marginal suitability status for predicted climatic conditions, under both moderate (RCP 45) and extreme (RCP 85) emission pathways.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Santa Maria della Versa Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2021–2050)

Santa Maria della Versa Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2036–2065)

Santa Maria della Versa Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2021–2050)

Santa Maria della Versa Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2036–2065)

Total Suitability Methodology for Pilot Sites

The total suitability assessment for viticulture was carried out across four selected pilot sites in the Oltrepò Pavese region: Montù Beccaria, Costa Cavalieri, Canevino, and Santa Maria della Versa. The methodology applied mirrors the one developed at the macro-scale, ensuring consistency in evaluating land suitability under actual climatic conditions.

For each pilot site, the three key macro-factors; climatic suitability, soil suitability, and topographic suitability (both developed by ERSAF) were integrated into a single total suitability score. Each macro-factor was represented by a raster map reclassified into five suitability classes (S1 to N2) and weighted according to its relative importance.

The three reclassified and weighted raster layers were combined using raster algebra within a GIS environment (QGIS or ArcGIS). The formula applied was:

$$\text{Total Suitability} = (\text{Climatic raster} \times 0.50) + (\text{Soil raster} \times 0.15) + (\text{Topography raster} \times 0.35)$$

The resulting continuous raster, ranging theoretically between 1.0 and 5.0, was then reclassified into five discrete classes:

S1 (Highly Suitable)	0.00 – 1.00
S2 (Suitable)	1.01 – 2.00
S3 (Moderately Suitable)	2.01 – 3.00
N1 (Currently Not Suitable)	3.01 – 4.00
N2 (Permanently Not Suitable)	>4.00

This integrated classification allows for a spatially explicit evaluation of the total suitability.

As regards the assessment of the total suitability for future climatic scenarios the methodological framework was identical to that used for the baseline assessment and described above, ensuring full comparability between present and future conditions.

Total Suitability Results for Pilot Sites (Actual Scenario)

The total suitability analysis under current climate conditions was conducted across the four pilot sites; Montù Beccaria, Costa Cavalieri, Canevino, and Santa Maria della Versa by integrating the previously assessed climatic, pedological, and topographic suitability layers. The integration was performed using weighted raster overlay, assigning a weight of 0.5 to the climatic layer, 0.15 to the soil layer, and 0.35 to the topographic layer.

Site-specific findings are summarized as follows:

Canevino: The total suitability map indicates full coverage under S2 (Moderately Suitable).

Costa Cavalieri: The site is also fully categorized within S2 (Moderately Suitable).

Montù Beccaria: Unlike the other sites, this area presents a more balanced distribution, with 51.42% classified as S2 (Moderately Suitable) and 48.58% as S3 (Marginally Suitable).

Santa Maria della Versa: The entirety of this site falls within S3 (Marginally Suitable).

Pilot Site	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Montù Beccaria	0.00	51.42%	48.58%	0.00	0.00
Costa Cavalieri	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Canevino	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Santa Maria della Versa	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00

The suitability classification demonstrates differentiation among the four pilot sites. The Montù Beccaria site shows a partial differentiation, splitting almost equally between S2 (51.42%) and S3 (48.58%). In contrast, Costa Cavalieri and Canevino remain uniformly within S2 (Moderately Suitable), while Santa Maria della Versa is classified entirely within S3 (Marginally Suitable). This overall pattern suggests a general coherence in regional environmental conditions, with localized variation at Montù Beccaria where pedological and topographic advantages may combine with less restrictive climatic conditions, leading to its mixed S2/S3 status. The other sites are uniformly classified based on their dominant limiting factors.

Total Suitability Pilot Sites MAPS

Canevino:

Costa Cavalieri:

Montù Beccaria:

Santa Maria della Versa:

Total Suitability Results of Pilot sites (Future Scenarios)

The total suitability analysis for viticulture under future climate conditions was conducted for the four pilot sites: Costa Cavalieri (CCV), Canevino (CNV), Montù Beccaria (POR), and Santa Maria della Versa (SMV), across four scenarios: RCP 45 (2021–2050), RCP 45 (2036–2065), RCP 85 (2021–2050), and RCP 85 (2036–2065).

The total suitability integrates climatic, pedological, and topographical factors into a single composite index, reclassified into five classes: S1 (Highly Suitable), S2 (Moderately Suitable), S3 (Marginally Suitable), N1 (Currently Not Suitable), and N2 (Permanently Not Suitable).

Costa Cavalieri (CCV)

Across all four scenarios, total suitability is dominated by S3 = 100% of the site area. No areas are projected to fall into S1, S2, N1 and N2. The persistence of this distribution suggests that climatic characteristic partially offset pedological and topographic limitations, but not sufficiently to achieve higher suitability categories.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 45 (2021-2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 45 (2036-2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 85 (2021-2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Costa Cavalieri	RCP 85 (2036-2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Costa Cavalieri Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050)

Costa Cavalieri Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065)

Costa Cavalieri Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050)

Costa Cavalieri Total Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065)

Canevino (CNV)

The total suitability classification for the entire Canevino (CNV) site varies depending on the emission trajectory. Under the moderate emission trajectory (RCP 45), 100% of the site area is consistently classified as S2 (Moderately Suitable) across both time horizons (2021–2050 and 2036–2065). However, under the high emission trajectory (RCP 85), 100% of the site area shifts to S3 (Marginally Suitable) for the same periods. This indicates that while the site maintains a suitable status in all future scenarios, the increase in emissions leads to a reduction in the degree of suitability.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Canevino	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	100	0	0	0
Canevino	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	100	0	0	0
Canevino	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Canevino	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Canevino Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050)

Canevino Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065)

Canevino Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050)

Canevino Total Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065)

Montù Beccaria (POR)

POR records S3 = 100% across all four scenarios. This indicates that all variables are in same range, resulting in a nearly uniform marginal suitability classification.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Montù Beccaria	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Montù Beccaria	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Montù Beccaria Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050)

Montù Beccaria Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065)

Montù Beccaria Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050)

Montù Beccaria Total Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065)

Santa Maria della Versa (SMV)

The entire site area is consistently classified entirely within S3 (marginally suitable) under all four future scenarios for Total Suitability. The absence of any class variation between scenarios suggests that the site maintains a marginally suitability status, under both moderate (RCP 45) and extreme (RCP 85) emission pathways.

Site	Scenario	S1 (%)	S2 (%)	S3 (%)	N1 (%)	N2 (%)
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 45 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 45 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 85 (2021–2050)	0	0	100	0	0
Santa Maria della Versa	RCP 85 (2036–2065)	0	0	100	0	0

Santa Maria della Versa Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050)

Santa Maria della Versa Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065)

Santa Maria della Versa Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050)

Santa Maria della Versa Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065)

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